

ORGANIZATION OF TRAFFIC AT UNCONTROLLED INTERSECTIONS

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Annotation: In this thesis, it is mentioned about the implementation of organizational work to prevent uncontrolled intersections and uncontrolled activities in them.

Keywords: intersection, dead intersections, motor vehicle, measures.

Аннотация: В данной тезисе упоминается о проведении организационных работ по предупреждению нерегулируемых перекрестков и неконтролируемых действий на них.

Ключевые слова: перекресток, мертвые перекрестки, автотранспорт, мероприятия.

As we know, traffic at intersections, the traffic rules at which are carried out on the basis of permanently defined rules. At uncontrolled intersections, officials must be constantly ready to organize re-management.

Traffic at an intersection.

-A driver turning left or right must give way to pedestrians crossing the carriageway of the intersecting road, as well as cyclists crossing the road from the bicycle lane.

-A driver who is forced to stop due to traffic, if he obstructs the movement of vehicles in the transverse direction, he is prohibited from entering the intersection or intersection of traffic sections.

-At a flashing yellow signal, traffic lights are not working or at non-regulatory intersections, drivers must follow the rules for passing through unregulated intersections, yield signs installed at the intersection.

Regulated intersections.

-The driver of a non-rail vehicle turning left or turning at a green signal of a traffic light must give way to vehicles moving straight and turning right from the opposite side. Tram drivers must also follow this rule.

-The driver of the vehicle moving in the direction of the guide on the green signal of the additional network lit at the same time as the red or yellow signal of the traffic light must give way to the vehicles of other directions.

- If a traffic light or signals of the regulator allow tram and non-rail vehicles to move at the same time, the tram has the right of way, regardless of the direction of traffic.

- The driver entering the intersection at the permissive sign of the traffic light must continue moving in the specified direction, regardless of the traffic light sign at the exit. However, if there are stop lines (or 5.33 signs) in front of the traffic lights located in the driver's path at the intersection, he must obey each traffic light signal.

- When the permissive sign of the traffic light is on, the driver must give way to vehicles completing the movement through the intersection and to pedestrians completing the passage in the appropriate direction.

Unregulated intersections.

- At an intersection where roads of no equal importance intersect, the driver of a vehicle coming from a secondary road must give way to a vehicle coming from the main road, regardless of the direction of further movement.

- The driver of a non-rail vehicle must give way to the vehicles coming from the right at the intersection of roads of equal importance.

This rule must also be followed by tram drivers. At such intersections, regardless of the following direction of traffic, the tram has the right of way over non-rail vehicles.

- When the direction of the main road changes at an intersection, drivers driving on the main road must follow the rule of passing through the intersection of roads of equal importance.

Drivers driving on secondary roads should also follow this rule.

- When turning to the left or turning, the driver of a non-rail vehicle must give way to vehicles moving straight or to the right from the opposite direction on an equally important road, as well as overtaking vehicles in permitted cases. This rule must also be followed by tram drivers.

- If the driver cannot determine whether the road on which he is driving is covered (dark time, mud, snow, etc.) and there are no concession signs, then he should consider himself to be on a secondary road.

Conclusion.

In conclusion, it can be noted that at all out-of-control intersections, if the relevant employees do not manage their activities in time, the restoration of control can be complicated.

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